

Recommendation 1

*Vereist

1. Is the code in a publicly accessible repository? If yes, write the name of the repository; if not, write "No" *

Recommendation 2

2. Is the code shared under a licence? If yes, write the name of the licence; if not, write "No" *

Recommendation 3

3. Is the code registered in a community registry? If yes, write the name of the community registry; if not, write "No" *

Recommendation 4

4. Is it possible to cite the software? If yes, write the last name of the first author; if not, write "No" *

Recommendation 5

5. Is there a software quality checklist? If yes, write who created it; if not, write "No". *

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